

1 STE(A)M Learning Ecologies and creativity: A typology of open schooling projects
2 based on stakeholder and learner engagement

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4 Running title: STE(A)M Learning Ecologies

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40 Acknowledgments

41 We are grateful to all learners and stakeholders who participated in the pilot STE(A)M
42 Learning Ecologies. This research was funded by the European Union's Horizon
43 program under Grant Agreement No 101094648. Views and opinions expressed are
44 those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union.
45 Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for
46 them.

47
48 Declaration of Interest

49 The authors have no conflict of interest to declare.

50 **STE(A)M Learning Ecologies and creativity: A typology of open schooling**
51 **projects based on stakeholder and learner engagement**

52

53 **1. Introduction**

54 Open schooling projects have been continuously funded over the last decade by the
55 European Union as a major investment to address declining student interest in STEM
56 careers, the gender gap in STEM, and the rather confined growth observed in science-
57 based innovation and entrepreneurship (STE(A)M Learning Ecologies, 2024). Open
58 schooling is based on the core premise that collaboration of formal education
59 providers with a diverse array of stakeholders, including non-formal education
60 providers and enterprises, would allow learners engage in real-life creative problem-
61 solving and stimulate interest in science (European Commission, 2015). In the same
62 report where it endorsed open schooling, the European Commission also highlighted
63 the need to move from STEM to STE(A)M, in order to integrate science, technology,
64 engineering, and mathematics with all (“A”) other subjects and disciplines (European
65 Commission, 2015). Such a focus on integration seems to be necessary for
66 operationalizing learners’ access to authentic learning contexts and overcoming the
67 siloed approach that still prevails in several European curricula. Open schooling is
68 expected to bridge formal learning with non-formal learning across educational levels,
69 make learning much more relevant and creative for learners and foster 21st century
70 skills (European Commission, 2024). The transformative change that open schooling
71 is hoped to achieve includes bringing learners beyond school walls and offering
72 opportunities for community engagement (STE(A)M Learning Ecologies, 2024). The
73 cross-fertilization of learning experiences from different learning settings would
74 ultimately enhance informed decision-making and community well-being, foster

75 career awareness and improve employability and competitiveness (European
76 Commission, 2024; Okada et al., 2024; STE(A)M Learning Ecologies, 2024).

77 Although open schooling has not yet been institutionalized in most European
78 countries (STE(A)M Learning Ecologies, 2024), several EU-funded projects have
79 adopted the open schooling perspective. The project that paved the way for open
80 schooling was “Open School for Open Societies – OSOS”, implemented between
81 2017 and 2020 (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/741572>). OSOS delivered an
82 “Open Schooling Roadmap for Schools” (Author et al., 2017), which described how
83 schools can be empowered to facilitate transformative change aiming towards open
84 schooling. This included: (1) reconceptualization of students as creators/producers
85 rather than consumers and their work as creation/production rather than consumption;
86 (2) securing innovative learning resources through networking with stakeholders; (3)
87 adopting an integrated STE(A)M educational approach; (4) fostering distributed
88 teacher leadership through peer learning and collaboration. The next waves of EU
89 projects on open schooling were funded under the action grants for “Open Schooling
90 and Collaboration on Science Education” in the 2018, 2019, and 2020 calls (11
91 projects, overall), and under the action grants for “Open Schooling for Science
92 Education and a Learning Continuum for All” in 2022 (another 3 projects). The 2018-
93 2020 projects were expected to: (1) promote school networking with stakeholders,
94 including industry partners and civil society organizations; and (2) empower schools
95 to become agents of community well-being. The emphasis in the last call in 2022
96 shifted from schools to whole stakeholder partnerships, in order to: (1) develop a rich
97 set of learning resources; (2) promote stakeholder engagement through participatory
98 processes; and (3) engage learners in real-life challenges to encourage creativity (for a
99 detailed account of all EU-funded open schooling projects, see Authors et al., 2023a).

100 Previous studies showed that open schooling projects can facilitate the
101 transformation of a considerable number of schools to innovation hubs within local
102 communities and across different countries (Author et al., 2021; Author et al., 2023).
103 Specifically, data collected in a pre-post-test arrangement from several hundred
104 schools engaged in the Open School for Open Societies – OSOS project showed that,
105 on average, these schools were successful in taking up innovation and adopting the
106 Open Schooling Roadmap (Author et al., 2021; Author et al., 2023). Indeed,
107 improvement was observed at the management and process levels, including vision,
108 leadership, and stakeholder involvement, as well as for teachers’ professional
109 development. Although the change was greater for schools that scored relatively low
110 in the pre-test measurements, there was also room for improvement for schools that
111 started with relatively high pre-test values. Previous research using instruments and
112 data collected within the framework of the CONNECT project (Inclusive Open
113 Schooling Through Engaging and Future-oriented Science – CONNECT;
114 <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/872814>) has documented that open schooling can
115 increase secondary school students’ connection with science, and more specifically,
116 that this is valid for both male and female learners (Okada, 2024). Another finding of
117 this research was that teachers highlighted how students’ interest in science led them
118 to engage in science activities beyond everyday school practice (Okada, 2024). Even
119 though the above results from OSOS and CONNECT are quite encouraging, more
120 evidence from more projects is needed to explore and justify the impact of open
121 schooling and to scale-up effective strategies and policies for its uptake and
122 sustainability across Europe.

123 Despite the considerable funding of open schooling projects from the EU,
124 relevant publications documenting stakeholder and learner engagement have been

125 scarce. To address this lack, we will present an analysis of open schooling initiatives
126 launched within the frame of the STE(A)M Learning Ecologies – SLEs project
127 (<https://www.steamecologies.eu/>). A STE(A)M learning ecology (SLE) promotes
128 stakeholder networking to contribute learning resources for learner engagement.
129 These are then employed by students to create learning artefacts, which reflect their
130 accumulating knowledge and skills. Authentic learning experiences are co-developed
131 by students, their teachers, and other stakeholders, while addressing real-world
132 problems. The pilot cycle of the project (September 2023-August 2024) involved 12
133 pilot SLEs in 12 European countries (Cyprus, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Malta,
134 Norway, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Spain). The mature cycle (September
135 2024-August 2025) will include at least 10 different SLEs in each of the reference
136 countries, and will build on lessons learnt and good practices gained during the pilot
137 cycle. To provide guidance and insight to new SLEs during the mature cycle, we
138 analyzed several data sources, for instance, the learning artefacts of students and two
139 templates completed by stakeholders in the pilot SLEs, namely, a participatory
140 pedagogical design template and a participatory scenario development template. The
141 main outcomes of our analysis include a typology of SLEs, and several design aspects
142 addressing stakeholder synthesis (diversity) and interaction, learning resources, and
143 support provided to learners. Based on these results, we will conclude with a set of
144 policy recommendations, which we expect to elaborate upon further with additional
145 data from the mature cycle of the project.

146

147 **1.1 STE(A)M Learning Ecologies and creativity**

148 Creativity has been defined as production of novel ideas, artefacts or solutions, which
149 can prove useful within a particular social context (Plucker et al., 2004; Runco &

150 Jaeger, 2012). The concept of SLEs offers the opportunity for creative collaboration
151 and outcomes in two dimensions, namely, stakeholder engagement and learner
152 engagement. First, a stakeholder acting as the initiator of the SLE (e.g. formal or non-
153 formal education provider or any other stakeholder) leads the establishment of a
154 stakeholder coalition, which makes available learning resources and support, and
155 works to arrange these resources along a learning activity sequence and create a
156 learning path. Second, students are invited to use learning resources and enact
157 learning activities to address a real-world problem. In doing so, students create
158 tangible and original learning artefacts. This configuration allows the stakeholder
159 network to set up an enabling environment for learning, which unfolds within a
160 unique social context. In that regard, SLEs foster a contextual and situated account of
161 creativity (Glăveanu et al., 2019; Van der Zanden et al., 2020), which facilitates both
162 stakeholder collaboration for pedagogical design as well as learner collaboration to
163 produce learning artefacts. Stakeholder diversity and supply of heterogeneous
164 learning resources can be instrumental for bridging formal and non-formal learning
165 settings, and offering novel and open-ended learning opportunities, which are not
166 favored in traditional classrooms (Richardson & Mishra, 2018). Stakeholder
167 involvement and the context-dependency of SLEs can prove decisive for perspective-
168 taking, which catalyzes the delivery of novel outcomes by students (Rubenstein et al.,
169 2019). Furthermore, co-creation of solutions to real-world challenges distributes
170 learning incentives across all actors involved, which means that all actors in an SLE
171 can serve simultaneously as educators and learners.

172 An SLE is a physical and socio-cultural learning context co-developed by
173 diverse stakeholders to engage students in STE(A)M. We consider learning products
174 (LPs) as the manifestation of student creativity in SLEs. We define LPs as any artefact

175 constructed by learners themselves, anytime they use learning resources to enact
176 learning activities (see Author, 2016a; Authors et al., 2018). LPs provide a solid
177 anchorage of SLEs in learner-centered pedagogical approaches based on
178 constructionism (Papert, 1993) and constructivism (Hmelo-Silver et al., 2007; Author,
179 2016) and can be physical or digital. Some products can have a more central place
180 within a sequence of learning activities and other products can have a more secondary
181 role. All LPs, however, reflect learner knowledge and skills and can be used to
182 diagnose learner performance and operationalize formative assessment, peer
183 assessment or summative assessment (Authors et al., 2014; Author, 2016a). Such an
184 option can address the gap reported by Perignat and Katz-Buonincontro (2019), who
185 highlighted the lack of empirical data documenting creativity in their integrative
186 review of literature on STEAM education published between 2007 and 2018. Even in
187 learning settings like makerspaces, where learner creativity in STE(A)M is explicitly
188 linked to the design and delivery of tangible artefacts, a thorough approach and
189 analysis of what students are able to create when employing tools to undertake
190 learning activities is largely lacking (Soomro et al., 2023). Using LPs for assessment
191 presents advantages over psychometrics with pre- and post-test scales, which are still
192 prevalent but tend to treat learner engagement as a “black box” (Kocak et al., 2021;
193 Richardson & Mishra, 2018; see also Soomro et al., 2023, in this regard). Moreover,
194 LPs may offer a solution for “decentralizing” both assessment and learner support
195 from educators, only, to other stakeholders engaged in open schooling projects, as
196 long as learners would be given the opportunity to present their work to these
197 stakeholders and benefit from their feedback and guidance (see Wilson, 2021).
198 Overall, LPs can facilitate an alignment of curriculum standards and pedagogical
199 design, implementation, and assessment, exactly because they reflect knowledge and

200 skills needed for their creation. Such an arrangement would be crucial for formal
201 education in order to strike an optimal balance between structure, on the one hand,
202 and flexibility, on the other, so that pedagogical design can sustain the open-ended
203 character of SLEs and allow learners to adapt LPs to their changing needs and desires
204 or changing contexts. Such balancing of freedom and guidance was singled out as
205 supportive of creativity development (Van der Zanden et al., 2020).

206 Learner engagement in SLEs is promoted within an overall vision of fusing
207 open schooling with integrated STEM learning or STE(A)M (Authors et al., 2023a).
208 Such a fusion seeks to integrate science, technology, engineering, and mathematics
209 not only with art, but with all (“A”) other subjects (European Commission, 2015),
210 including humanities and the social sciences (Quigley et al., 2017). Integration aims
211 to develop the STE(A)M literacy needed to address real-world problems, which
212 cannot be satisfied by approaching different subjects and disciplines in a fragmented
213 manner. It also signifies the considerable challenge of handling the increased
214 complexity of content marked by interdisciplinarity. There have been numerous calls
215 for respecting the autonomy and distinguishing features of each different discipline,
216 while opting for STE(A)M (Langlois et al., 2024; Tytler et al., 2021). To this end, a
217 much more robust epistemological discussion is necessary to better justify integrated
218 STEM proposals (McComas & Burgin, 2020; Ortiz-Revilla et al., 2020). At the same
219 time, however, integration harbors opportunities for innovation, because creative
220 solutions usually emerge at the interface between disciplines (European Commission,
221 2015). In this regard, recent contributions shed light on cross-cutting themes, for
222 instance, modelling, which could offer valid bridges across disciplines (Develaki,
223 2020; Reynante et al., 2020), and proposed theoretical frameworks, which can
224 illustrate shared characteristics in the nature of knowledge and inquiry practices to

225 overcome disciplinary silos (Quinn et al., 2020). In line with such approaches, our
226 perspective allows integration to be discussed from both an instructional and a
227 learning perspective. This implies that designing STE(A)M open schooling projects
228 should take advantage of all possible capacity and interactions between stakeholders
229 when it comes to supplying content; however, learners also need to be ready and
230 competent to handle content complexity. In this regard, SLEs need to embrace 21st
231 century skills, which are indispensable for addressing interdisciplinarity and lifelong
232 learning (Authors et al., 2023a; see also Bequette & Bequette, 2012), for instance,
233 communication, collaboration, critical thinking and problem solving, creativity and
234 innovation (European Commission, 2019; OECD, 2019). This adds another aspect to
235 the pedagogical design of SLEs, one that indicates a shift towards process-based
236 learning (European Commission, 2015) to foster 21st century skills.

237 Stakeholder engagement in a SLE includes the following main stages, which
238 are needed to develop a unique learning setting enabling learner engagement and
239 operationalize the SLE concept: (1) Getting started: An SLE starts with an initiator
240 (provider of formal or non-formal education or any other stakeholder taking the lead)
241 singling out a real-world challenge to work with. Some first learning objectives can be
242 formulated already at this stage, but these will be enriched when more stakeholders
243 join the SLE. (2) Building the partnership: Stakeholder mapping is paramount here to
244 identify public, private and civil society organizations that can offer learning
245 resources. The SLEs consortium deemed a minimum of the initiator plus two different
246 stakeholders to be necessary for securing learning resources and learner support
247 (Authors et al., 2023b). (3) Co-creating the SLE: Stakeholders co-create the main
248 learning paths. These demarcate learning resources available along a sequence of
249 learning activities, LPs to be created by learners, and support to be provided to

250 learners. (4) Implementing and monitoring the SLE: To scaffold stakeholder
251 interaction and learner engagement, two templates are completed by stakeholders. The
252 participatory pedagogical design template (Appendix A) describes key aspects of
253 learner engagement. The participatory scenario development template (Appendix B)
254 describes different scenarios for stakeholder engagement in terms of resources and
255 time to be invested. Both templates are revisited when learners are engaged, for
256 monitoring the SLE, taking any corrective action, if needed, and optimizing the
257 impact and sustainability of the SLE. (5) Documenting learner engagement: All actors
258 reflect upon LPs created by learners as a manifestation of learner engagement.

259

260 **1.2 Research questions**

261 The research questions to be addressed in this paper are the following:

262 (1) What types of SLEs can we identify based on their pedagogical design and
263 learning path (e.g. learning resources, sequencing of learning activities), as well as the
264 LPs created by students?

265 (2) What are the similarities and differences between types of SLEs in terms of
266 learner and stakeholder engagement?

267

268 Having a typology of SLEs will offer the opportunity to delve deeper into the
269 strengths and weaknesses of each type of SLE as far as learner and stakeholder
270 engagement are concerned, provide much more user-tailored guidance to new SLEs to
271 be established, suggest directions for future research, and streamline policy
272 recommendations to achieve optimal investment of resources and impact.

273

274 **2. Methods**

275

276 2.1 Participants

277 Participants were stakeholders and learners in 12 SLEs. Table 1 presents the
278 descriptive characteristics for all 12 SLEs in the pilot phase of the project. There was
279 considerable variety in terms of challenges addressed and geographical coverage,
280 including locations in the Mediterranean (ES, CY, IT, PT, GR, MT), the Balkans (RO,
281 RS), central Europe (SK, DE), and Northern Europe (IE, NO). Most SLEs were
282 initiated by providers of non-formal education (IE, ES, PT, DE, RS) and formal
283 education (NO, RO, SK, GR), while 2 SLEs were set up by governmental
284 organizations (CY, MT) and another SLE was launched by a civil society organization
285 (IT). With regard to learners' ages, SLEs covered all educational levels, from lower
286 primary education to higher education (Table 1). Table 2 shows the representation of
287 different types of stakeholders across SLEs, for instance, providers of formal
288 education (e.g., primary and secondary schools, universities) and non-formal
289 education (e.g., research institutes), governmental organizations (e.g., Ministries),
290 civil society organizations (e.g., non-governmental organizations), and industry
291 partners. Overall, there were 96 stakeholders engaged, with a median of 7.5
292 stakeholders per SLE (min across the 12 SLEs = 4; max = 13). Most numerous were
293 formal education providers ($n = 28$; $Mdn = 2$; min = 1; max = 4) followed by industry
294 partners ($n = 23$; $Mdn = 1$; min = 0; max = 11), non-formal education providers ($n =$
295 20 ; $Mdn = 1$; min = 0; max = 4), governmental organizations ($n = 18$; $Mdn = 1$; min =
296 0 ; max = 3), and civil society organizations ($n = 7$; $Mdn = 1$; min = 0; max = 1)¹.
297 SLEs engaged 1079 learners, overall (min = 11; max = 450). There was considerable
298 heterogeneity in the number of learners across SLEs, with three SLEs, hosting a much
299 higher number of learners than the median of 30 (RS = 450; PT = 188; GR = 175).

300

301 *2.2 Procedure*

302 The establishment and operation of SLEs closely followed the life cycle presented in
303 Section 1.1. Initiators were either project partners themselves (see, for example, the
304 SLEs in NO, IT, DE, and GR) or stakeholders connected with project partners who
305 served as initiators (see, for instance, the SLEs in IE, ES, CY, and SK). After initiators
306 outlined the challenge to be addressed in the SLE and formulated some preliminary
307 learning objectives, they proceeded with building the partnership through stakeholder
308 mapping and contacting potential stakeholders. A core group of stakeholders was set
309 up in each location, which took over co-creating the SLE, specifically, identifying
310 learning resources, arranging them along learning paths, and describing the LPs to be
311 expected from learners and the support to be provided to learners for creating these
312 products. All SLEs had a minimum learner engagement duration of approximately 40
313 hours. As each SLE developed and learner engagement advanced, more stakeholders
314 would be invited to join based on learner and stakeholder needs and desires. During
315 the implementation of each SLE, stakeholders worked with a template for
316 participatory pedagogical design to plan and formatively assess learner engagement,
317 as well as a participatory scenario development template to evaluate stakeholder
318 engagement. Project partners acted as initiators or as national coordinators
319 maintaining close contact with all stakeholders in SLEs, providing guidance anytime
320 needed and informing stakeholders about the progress of the SLEs project. The
321 process concluded with documenting each SLE, which involved collecting: (1)
322 participatory pedagogical design templates, (2) participatory scenario development
323 templates, (3) LPs created by learners, (4) stakeholder interviews, (5) questionnaires
324 completed by national coordinators.

325

326 *2.3 Data Sources*

327 We used the items delivered to document SLEs as our data sources. The template for
328 participatory pedagogical design was completed for each SLE with stakeholder input
329 (Appendix A). Stakeholders described learning resources, arranged them along
330 learning paths, and outlined LPs expected from learners (Authors, 2023a). This
331 template also included a curriculum mapping of LPs based on the knowledge and
332 skills necessary for their creation, the support learners would need from stakeholders,
333 and the total duration of learner engagement. Finally, stakeholders commented on the
334 attractiveness of the learning paths to both male and female learners and related career
335 opportunities. The template for participatory scenario development was also
336 completed with stakeholder input (Appendix B) and referred to stakeholder synthesis
337 and interaction, the learning resources available and learner support. This template
338 enabled stakeholders to allocate resources efficiently and take corrective action
339 whenever needed (Authors, 2023b). Business-as-usual scenarios portrayed baseline
340 conditions under no additional stakeholder investment; small-effort scenarios outlined
341 desirable results under minimal input; best-case scenarios depicted ideal futures under
342 optimal investment. Moreover, we detailed metadata of all LPs gathered in each SLE
343 to document the creative outcomes of learner engagement (see Data analysis).
344 Stakeholder interviews concentrated on the local context, the stakeholders engaged,
345 their prior experience with open schooling, the challenges encountered, the benefits
346 and added value of the SLE, learner engagement, SLEs' sustainability, and
347 suggestions for improvement. The questionnaire completed by national coordinators
348 focused on learning outcomes, how stakeholders facilitated learning, female

349 participation, educators' experiences, impact of the policy framework, challenges
350 encountered, and stakeholder collaboration.

351

352 *2.4 Ethics, data protection, and ethical approval*

353 All stakeholders who were interviewed provided their informed consent before the
354 interviews started and after they were briefed about the SLEs project, data collection
355 and data processing. The participation in the interviews was voluntary and anonymous
356 and interviews lasted, on average, about 30min. All data were pseudonymized and
357 kept in a digital repository. Access to the data repository was provided to members of
358 project partners involved in the research for pursuing the objectives of the project,
359 namely, for processing data to draft the deliverables of the project and scientific
360 publications. Interviewees were informed that all personal data would be destroyed 5
361 years after the completion of the project, until the period eligible for a full audit by the
362 Granting Authority has expired. They were also informed that they had the right to
363 withdraw their participation at any time without having any consequences. All
364 procedures followed by project partners with regard to ethics and data protection were
365 described in detail in a deliverable of the SLEs project titled Ethics Monitoring
366 Mechanism (Deliverable D1.2). This deliverable is EU Classified and includes the
367 procedures followed for each country to secure an ethical clearance, including
368 informed consent forms. For instance, data collection and processing in Cyprus,
369 which was undertaken in the frame of the SLEs project, received approval from the
370 Department of Secondary General Education of Cyprus' Ministry of Education, Sport
371 and Youth (Reference number 07.15.004.015.004/5 October 2023), while ethical
372 clearance for data collection and processing in Norway received approval from the
373 Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research – Sikt (Reference

374 number 415352/25 May 2023). Although there were interviewees in this research
375 from two countries which are not EU Members States (Norway; Serbia), there was no
376 transfer of personal data of interviewees in any EU Member States to these two
377 countries. Personal data of minors were not collected in this research.

378

379 *2.5 Data Analysis*

380 We first analyzed the templates for participatory pedagogical design completed with
381 stakeholder input and the LPs delivered by learners in each SLE. This allowed us to
382 develop a typology of SLEs based on design characteristics and the main outcomes of
383 learner engagement. The first author went multiple times through all templates and
384 LPs and initiated a categorization of SLEs based on the template and metadata
385 identification based on the characteristics of the LPs. More specifically, the coding
386 criteria at this stage were the learning paths including learning resources and learning
387 products, sequencing of learning activities, flexibility in pedagogical design, and
388 trade-offs (e.g. incompatible features in pedagogical design and potential
389 compromises between them; see Table 3). Initial categories of SLEs were
390 reconsidered as data analyses proceeded, and the coding process concluded with a
391 final set of SLEs types. A second coder, who is a researcher at the University of
392 Cyprus, Research in Science and Technology Education Group, and has considerable
393 experience in STEM teaching and participation in several STEM projects funded by
394 the EU, and who did not participate in drafting the initial SLEs categories and
395 metadata, repeated the coding process, with a Cohen's kappa greater than 0.85. In the
396 present paper we will refer mainly to the typology of SLEs and present some
397 characteristic LPs in each category, without delving deeper on their metadata. In the
398 second stage of data analysis, we processed the templates for participatory scenario

399 development, interviews, and questionnaires, to explore if there were any major trends
400 across types of SLEs in terms of stakeholder engagement. In this case, the coding
401 criteria were determined by the structure of the participatory scenario development
402 template, the interview protocol and the questionnaire. These involved, for instance,
403 stakeholder synthesis, learning objectives, potential for change (e.g. departure from
404 business-as-usual conditions based on varying stakeholder input and contribution),
405 challenges related to establishing and operating SLEs, and sustainability of SLEs.
406 This second coding process was undertaken again by the first author, who developed
407 and refined codes after repeated readings of the data sources. Inter-rater reliability was
408 calculated in this case as well with the aid of the second same coder at the University
409 of Cyprus, with a Cohen's kappa greater than 0.85. Before the second coder repeated
410 the coding process, for both the first and second stage of analysis, there was an initial
411 discussion between the first and second coder focusing on coding criteria and
412 procedures for all data sources as well as research objectives. After the second coder
413 completed the coding process and Cohen's kappa was computed, mismatches between
414 the two coders were identified and these divergences were settled through a
415 discussion between the two coders. Given that the Cohen's kappa in our coding
416 processes was quite high (>0.85), mismatches were not numerous, so there was no
417 need to develop any elaborate resolution protocol for coder disagreements.

418

419 **3. Results**

420

421 *3.1 Typology of STE(A)M Learning Ecologies*

422 Table 3 presents the typology of SLEs in the pilot cycle of the project. The aspects
423 addressed for each type include the learning path including learning resources and

424 LPs, sequencing of learning activities, flexibility in pedagogical design, and trade-offs
425 in design aspects. Learner-experience oriented SLEs comprised the majority of
426 STE(A)M Learning Ecologies (IE; IT; PT; RO; DE; MT) in the pilot phase. Learners
427 in this type of SLE delivered a rich portfolio of diverse LPs making use of dedicated
428 learning resources offered by stakeholders (see examples in Figures 1 & 2 from the
429 Learner-experience oriented SLE titled “Steaming up with nature’s wonders”; RO,
430 Ramnicu Valcea). With regard to sequencing of learning activities, SLEs in this
431 category were quite modular, because learning activities did not presuppose each
432 other or did not follow a strict serial sequence and their order could be switched.
433 Flexibility of the pedagogical design was further promoted by the fact that learning
434 activities and LPs could be skipped or new activities could be added without any
435 major impact on the learning path or the overall learner experience. A trade-off in
436 Learner-experience oriented SLEs, however, was that the addition of learning
437 activities and products, which could obviously enhance learner experience in the short
438 term, could compromise the coherence of learner engagement and long-term learning
439 outcomes.

440 A second type of SLE was Master-product oriented SLEs (ES; SK). Here, all
441 learner work converged on a master LP, which was delivered at the end of the learning
442 path. This master LP integrated all prior LPs or needed them to be created (Figure 3
443 presents an example from the Master-product oriented SLE titled “AI in ecology –
444 ecology in AI”; SK, Poprad). Sequencing of LPs was organized around the master-
445 product, which could be presented to various audiences to demonstrate learners’
446 delivery, and which could also be used to propose and launch policy initiatives.
447 Flexibility of the pedagogical design was fostered by the fact that prior LPs could be
448 adapted to suit different learning contexts, provided that the overall structure as

449 determined by the features of the master product was maintained. Trade-offs in this
450 case were related to allocation of time and workload between all necessary prior LPs
451 and the master product.

452 End-user oriented SLEs were the third type of SLE (NO; RS). In these cases,
453 learners were tasked to design and create a key LP that addressed end-user needs and
454 desires (Figure 4 displays an example from the End-user oriented SLE titled “Student
455 software solutions for real clients”; NO, Trondheim). To do so, learners followed a
456 number of iterations, which involved a pronounced co-creation dimension in direct
457 contact to stakeholders in the SLE, who acted as the end-users. The co-creation
458 process marked the sequencing of learning activities, which unfolded as a product
459 development lifecycle having considerable resemblance to an iterative engineering
460 design process. In terms of flexibility, each design in this type of SLE was unique, in
461 the sense that key products had to meet different end-user needs and desires. A major
462 trade-off was that the innovation and creativity of learners and end-users needed to be
463 weighed against narrowing down their options so that realism (i.e., what was doable
464 given available resources) was maintained along the learning path.

465 The fourth and final category of SLEs was Citizen-science oriented SLEs (CY;
466 GR). Learners in these SLEs used a pre-determined data collection methodology to
467 contribute to a wider process building on such data, which was supported by multiple
468 social actors in multiple locations (An example from the Citizen-science oriented SLE
469 titled “Studying earthquakes”; Greece, Athens, is shown in Figure 5). As far as the
470 learning activity sequence is concerned, learners first got familiarized with the
471 methodology. Then, they collected data, inserted them into a broader database,
472 analyzed data, and concluded with policy implications. Flexibility was added to the
473 pedagogical design by the fact that policy recommendations and initiatives provided

474 further opportunities for stakeholder engagement and extension of the SLE. The trade-
475 offs encountered mostly referred to an optimal balance that needed to be found
476 between the rigidity of the methodology, on the one hand, and innovation in terms of
477 policy recommendations and initiatives, on the other.

478 In Figure 6, we present the four types of SLEs in a visual depiction, where
479 dark rhombuses represent LPs, and the dark line running through LPs represents the
480 learning path and activity sequence. In Learner-experience oriented SLEs (1), learning
481 activities and the delivery of LPs do not follow any strict serial sequence but can be
482 switched in order, without that having any impact on the learning path. This is
483 indicated by the cyclical arrangement of LPs. In Master-product oriented SLEs (2),
484 one final LP is singled out (master-product), which is delivered at the end of the
485 learning activity sequence, and which integrates all prior LPs or needs them to be
486 created. This configuration is portrayed by arrows starting from all LPs and heading
487 towards the master-product. In End-user oriented SLEs (3), the learning path evolves
488 along an iterative process, where learners co-design and optimize in close
489 collaboration with end-users a key LP, which addresses concrete end-user needs and
490 desires. This is represented by the helix-shaped learning activity sequence. In Citizen-
491 science oriented SLEs (4), the learning activity sequence involves two phases: First,
492 learners follow a pre-specified methodology to collect and analyze data (continuous
493 cycle on the top); second, they formulate policy recommendations based on their data,
494 and invite new stakeholders in the SLE to pursue these initiatives (dashed cycle at the
495 bottom). Overall, the different types of SLEs seem to correspond to different
496 strategies employed to address real-world problems in open schooling projects, for
497 instance, studying different dimension of a problem (Learner-experience oriented
498 SLEs), developing and presenting a solution to a problem to raise awareness (Master-

499 product oriented SLEs), following a product development lifecycle to address specific
500 needs and desires of end-users (End-user oriented SLEs), and co-designing policy
501 recommendations with stakeholders and launching participatory initiatives (Citizen-
502 science oriented SLEs).

503

504 *3.2 Similarities and Differences between Types of STE(A)M Learning Ecologies*

505

506 3.2.1 Stakeholder and learner engagement

507 The average total number of stakeholders engaged was least in the Master-product
508 oriented SLEs (*Mdn* = 4.5) and maximum in the End-user oriented SLEs (*Mdn* =
509 10.5) (see also Table 2 for an overview of all SLEs). The latter category also had the
510 most industry partners (*Mdn* = 7), who acted as end-users of the key LPs delivered by
511 learners. Citizen-science oriented SLEs were the most diverse type in terms of
512 stakeholder synthesis (number of different categories of stakeholders engaged) (*Mdn*
513 = 4.5), while Learner-experience oriented SLEs was the least diverse (*Mdn* = 3.5). For
514 Citizen-science oriented SLEs, policy recommendations and initiatives capitalizing on
515 citizen science data could increase stakeholder heterogeneity substantially during the
516 lifecycle of the SLE. Learner-experience oriented SLEs included the most formal
517 education providers (*Mdn* = 3) and non-formal education providers (*Mdn* = 3), despite
518 their relatively lower stakeholder diversity. This should be carefully considered and
519 weighed for scaling up STE(A)M learning ecologies. As far as number of learners are
520 concerned, there was quite high variation across and within SLE types. More data
521 from the mature phase of our project will be needed to see if there are any differences
522 in the number and age of learners across types of SLEs.

523

524 3.2.2 Learning objectives

525 All SLEs targeted 21st century skills (e.g., communication, collaboration, critical
526 thinking and problem solving, creativity and innovation), implying the importance of
527 this skillset for all challenges to be addressed and for open schooling, overall. Such
528 references were widespread in both the interviews with stakeholders and the
529 responses of national coordinators to the questionnaire. The following extracts
530 describe how bridging formal learning settings with non-formal learning
531 environments as well as learners' collaborative work in SLEs could promote 21st
532 century skills:

533

534 *Stepping out of the box of the usual work of the school and the teaching*
535 *process brings teachers and students to a more informal form of*
536 *communication...Also, creativity, communication, collaboration skills,*
537 *organization of work and the ability to perform in public crystallize as*
538 *important skills that young people develop in this way of collaboration...*

539 (Interview with representative of non-formal education provider; RS,
540 Belgrade)

541

542 *Collaborative work allowed students to improve team building skills,*
543 *collaboration and management of contrasting ideas.* (Questionnaire completed
544 by the national coordinator; MT, Pembroke)

545

546 Most SLEs (10 out of 12) included data collection and interpretation skills among
547 their desirable learning objectives. Furthermore, some Learner-experience oriented
548 SLEs targeted digital skills (IE; DE; MT), computational thinking skills (PT; RO;

549 MT), and experimentation skills (PT; RO; DE). End-used oriented SLEs (NO; RS)
550 noted entrepreneurial skills among their learning objectives, while Citizen-science
551 SLEs (CY; GR) prioritized modelling skills. All SLEs relied on female role models to
552 attract and sustain the participation of female learners. This was primarily
553 operationalized through female representatives or stakeholder spokespersons. These
554 are two characteristic extracts from questionnaires referring to female role models:

555

556 *During this process, all those who worked with the students in leadership roles*
557 *were female – scientists, teachers, workshop leaders, librarians, artists etc.*

558 *This was a conscious decision to use the principle of ‘See it – Be it’.*

559 (Questionnaire completed by the national coordinator; IE, Galway)

560

561 *During the pathway, stakeholders presented the list of five Italian excellent*
562 *female scientists who are on the list of the 100 most influential female*
563 *scientists. Contrary to other situations where the male component tends to*
564 *strive more to be in the spotlight and impose itself on the female component, in*
565 *this context, instead, boys and girls worked on a parity basis. (Questionnaire*
566 *completed by the national coordinator; IT, Rome)*

567

568 End-user oriented SLEs (NO; RS) included an elaborate co-creation process engaging
569 learners and end-users (industry partners) in iterations before the final version of the
570 key LP was delivered. Such an arrangement proved quite instrumental for promoting
571 career opportunities. In other types of SLEs, career opportunities were usually linked
572 with the contributions of stakeholder spokespersons.

573

574 3.2.3 Change

575 Templates for participatory scenario development conveyed stakeholder input on
576 three different scenarios: (1) current conditions (business-as-usual scenarios),
577 including gaps and inconsistencies to address when implementing SLEs; (2) small-
578 scale inputs that could prove crucial for achieving considerable progress
579 in the short term (small-effort scenarios); and (3) ideal conditions for SLEs to flourish
580 and achieve long-term sustainability (best-case scenarios). Stakeholders in each SLE
581 started with business-as-usual and then indicated changes in the other two scenarios.
582 A key finding across all types of SLEs was that small-effort scenarios marked a
583 departure from business-as-usual, indicating a qualitative change in prior conditions
584 that promoted all aspects of stakeholder engagement in SLEs (i.e., stakeholder
585 synthesis, stakeholder interaction, learning resources available, support provided to
586 learners). Such qualitative change was transformative in character because it signified
587 progression beyond business-as-usual. This finding implies that open schooling can
588 be initiated with small-scale inputs only, which may nonetheless have decisive
589 impact. It also points to small wins as drivers for scaling up open schooling. Indeed,
590 adding even a small number of stakeholders in an SLE for the realization of small-
591 effort scenarios seems to have initiated a positive feedback loop, where an increase in
592 stakeholder synthesis enhanced stakeholder interaction, which led to increased
593 availability of learning resources for learner engagement (Learner-experience oriented
594 SLEs) and increased support offered to learners (all types of SLEs). This catalytic
595 response addressed certain bottleneck effects described in business-as-usual scenarios,
596 where teachers working alone could not always be ready to provide all of the quality
597 feedback needed by learners. Here are excerpts from the participatory scenario

598 development in the German SLE, laying out the change from business-as-usual to
599 small-effort scenarios in terms of learning resources and support provided to learners:

600

601 *Students work with easily accessible resources to complete their projects. For*
602 *some ideas, only theoretical models are available to them. (Participatory*
603 *scenario development, Learning resources available, Business-as-usual*
604 *scenario; DE, Berlin)*

605

606 *Students can work with researchers to conduct small experiments with real*
607 *materials and in real scenarios. They gain new knowledge and practical skills*
608 *to implement their research ideas. (Participatory scenario development,*
609 *Learning resources available, Small-effort scenario; DE, Berlin)*

610

611 *The teacher supports the students according to their possibilities. However, it*
612 *is not always possible to meet all needs as this requires a lot of work and time.*
613 *(Participatory scenario development, Support provided to learners, Business-*
614 *as-usual scenario; DE, Berlin)*

615

616 *Supervisors are available at the individual learning stations to support the*
617 *teacher and help the students carry out their research projects. (Participatory*
618 *scenario development, Support provided to learners, Small-effort scenario;*
619 *DE, Berlin)*

620

621 In some cases, the qualitative change from business-as-usual to small-effort scenarios
622 was accompanied by quantitative change from small-effort to best-case scenarios.

623 This was often observed for Learner-experience oriented SLEs and Master-product
624 oriented SLEs, specifically, in terms of stakeholder synthesis and stakeholder
625 interaction. This indicates that these types of SLEs had an increased likelihood of
626 growing further, provided that more stakeholders joined and propelled their
627 interaction. This was exemplified in the example below from the SLE in Spain,
628 showcasing the transition in stakeholder synthesis from the business-as-usual
629 scenario, through the small-effort scenario, to the best-case scenario:

630

631 *A science museum initiates a collaboration with educational, research, science*
632 *school club, youth association and industry stakeholders to create an SLE on*
633 *artificial intelligence. (Participatory scenario development, Stakeholder*
634 *synthesis, Business-as-usual scenario; ES, A Coruña)*

635

636 *The incorporation of an audiovisual content company linked to artificial*
637 *intelligence brings a different perspective that enriched and provided the key*
638 *to the design of the SLE. (Participatory scenario development, Stakeholder*
639 *synthesis, Small-effort scenario; ES, A Coruña)*

640

641 *The partnership is maintained and incorporates new actors to enable the SLE*
642 *to be implemented in new contexts. (Participatory scenario development,*
643 *Stakeholder synthesis, Best-case scenario; ES, A Coruña)*

644

645 Other transitions involved the same initial qualitative change as above, from business-
646 as-usual to small-effort scenarios, followed by another qualitative change from small-
647 effort to best-case scenarios. This is illustrated in the sequence below from the

648 Norwegian SLE, showing the continuous qualitative change in terms of stakeholder
649 interaction from business-as-usual, through small-effort, to best-case scenarios:

650

651 *Professors and teacher assistants guide students, but the focus is primarily on*
652 *academic knowledge, with limited exposure to real-life experiences.*

653 (Participatory scenario development, Stakeholder interaction, Business-as-
654 usual scenario; NO, Trondheim)

655

656 *Occasional workshops and guest lectures by industry professionals provide*
657 *insights into real-life applications and current trends.* (Participatory scenario
658 development, Stakeholder interaction, Small-effort scenario; NO, Trondheim)

659

660 *Regular meetings between students, teacher assistants, and industry*
661 *representatives enable the discussion of project progress and overcoming any*
662 *potential obstacle.* (Participatory scenario development, Stakeholder
663 interaction, Best-case scenario; NO, Trondheim)

664

665 Qualitative change was reflected in a second form of positive feedback loop, which
666 was more expressed in Citizen-science oriented SLEs. In these cases, best-case
667 scenarios concentrated on peer interaction of either teachers, stakeholders, or learners,
668 which fostered both the availability of learning resources and the support provided to
669 learners (teacher, expert, or peer support). Developments of that kind revealed an
670 orientation towards SLE growth based on developing and sustaining communities of
671 practice. Overall, qualitative transitions in participatory scenario development
672 indicated that the transformative potential for change and innovation in SLEs was

673 considerable. Here is a characteristic example of that from the Cypriot SLE,
674 showcasing a qualitative transition from one scenario category to the next as far as
675 availability of learning resources is concerned:

676

677 *Resources available mainly stem from the Open University of Cyprus and*
678 *include: (1) A guide with the methodology for butterfly data collection; (2) an*
679 *application for identifying butterfly species; (3) a database for storing*
680 *butterfly data. (Participatory scenario development, Learning resources*
681 *available, Business-as-usual scenario; CY, Nicosia)*

682

683 *Stakeholders “inherit” the learning products of student projects and make*
684 *them available to other students, who can use them as learning resources; this*
685 *is currently facilitated through the contribution of the Natural Museum of*
686 *Dali, which hosts learning products of the butterfly project. (Participatory*
687 *scenario development, Learning resources available, Small-effort scenario;*
688 *CY, Nicosia)*

689

690 *Provided that more stakeholders join, especially the Department of Forests in*
691 *Cyprus and firms offering gardener services, these are expected to offer*
692 *additional learning resources and increase the variety of learning products,*
693 *which can be expected from the butterfly project. (Participatory scenario*
694 *development, Learning resources available, Best-case scenario; CY, Nicosia)*

695

696 3.2.4 Challenges

697 A series of challenges related to establishing and operating SLEs were stressed for
698 Learner-experience oriented SLEs and Master-product oriented SLEs. These
699 predominantly included constraints on the time that could be invested in SLEs, lack of
700 resources necessary to undertake implementation, curriculum constraints, and other
701 constraints imposed by the wider policy framework. Such challenges were typical of
702 formal education settings anytime educational interventions deviated from what was
703 typically prescribed in the curriculum. There were also a few contradictions identified,
704 which mainly referred to a gap between declarations by policymakers and policy
705 influencers, on the one hand, and what was finally allowed or possible to happen on
706 the ground, on the other. Here are two extracts of that kind, concentrating on the
707 contradictions of the policy framework in Romania and Slovakia:

708

709 *The current policy framework...can both support and constrain the*
710 *implementation of SLEs, depending on various factors such as funding,*
711 *regulations, and educational priorities...School leadership encourages the*
712 *participation in such initiatives, offering all the equipment needed.*

713 *Unfortunately, primary schools cannot readily access science or ICT labs, so*
714 *it is only within the frame of such projects that we can benefit from them.*

715 (Questionnaire completed by the national coordinator; RO, Ramnicu Valcea)

716

717 *The current policy framework in the context of implementing the SLE can have*
718 *both positive and negative impacts on its implementation... Policies that*
719 *prioritize and support STEAM education initiatives can provide a conducive*
720 *environment for the implementation of the SLE, as it aligns with the goals of*
721 *promoting interdisciplinary learning and real-world applications...Insufficient*

722 *funding or budget constraints within the policy framework can hinder the*
723 *successful implementation of the SLE, limiting resources for educational*
724 *activities, materials, and teacher training... (Questionnaire completed by the*
725 *national coordinator; SK, Poprad)*

726

727 Challenges for End-user oriented SLEs and Citizen-science oriented SLEs mainly
728 related to sustaining or renewing the stakeholder network.

729

730 3.2.5 Sustainability

731 Sustainability of SLEs was primarily supply-driven in Learner-experience oriented
732 SLEs and Master-product oriented SLEs, while it seemed to be demand-driven in
733 End-user oriented SLEs and Citizen-science oriented SLEs. Supply-driven
734 sustainability relied on the readiness of stakeholders to join and offer learning
735 resources or on their ability and willingness to reaffirm their participation, delivery,
736 and support. Demand-driven sustainability built on the iterative co-creation process of
737 learners with industry partners in the case of End-user oriented SLEs, which seemed
738 to create additional demand for end-user LPs on the part of industry partners. For
739 Citizen-science oriented SLEs, demand-driven sustainability depended upon peer
740 networks wishing to extend data collection and the potential impact on relevant
741 policy. The following interview extracts highlight how additional demand catalyzed
742 the sustainability of End-user oriented SLEs (examples from Norway and Serbia) and
743 how peer networks and policy implications promoted the sustainability of Citizen-
744 science oriented SLEs (two examples from Cyprus):

745

746 *This SLE ... is expected to run the following years too. Collaborations with the*
747 *customers are initiated and sustained in the future, for example some*
748 *customers may have project proposals for the students every year (Interview*
749 *with instructor at a higher education institute; NO, Trondheim)*

750

751 *For now, as far as the construction of the physical school gym is concerned,*
752 *there are indications that our partner could be the city and local authorities...*
753 *(Interview with representative of non-formal education provider; RS,*
754 *Belgrade)*

755

756 *The Butterfly project is implemented for a second subsequent year in the*
757 *school. The students who took part last year were kindly requested to inform*
758 *the students who joined this year about...the methodology followed to identify*
759 *butterflies. This way, students are much better able to grasp the*
760 *methodology... (Interview with teacher; CY, Nicosia)*

761

762 *Students were concerned about the fact that we did not find many butterfly*
763 *species along the transect and formulated their own hypotheses why this was*
764 *the case, for instance, that...there were not too many flowering plant species*
765 *to attract butterflies...this is how the need emerged to contact the Forest*
766 *Service. (Interview with teacher; CY, Nicosia)*

767

768 **4. Discussion and implications**

769 Based on the data sources we used, we were able to classify SLEs into four types: (1)
770 Learner-experience oriented, (2) Master-product oriented, (3) End-user oriented, and

771 (4) Citizen-science oriented. Table 4 summarizes the main features for each SLE type.
772 Learner-experience oriented SLEs were the most frequent but least diverse type;
773 however, they hosted the maximum number of formal and non-formal education
774 providers. Master-product oriented SLEs had the least stakeholders and End-user
775 oriented SLE the most, primarily industry partners. Citizen-science oriented SLEs
776 were the most diverse type of SLE. All SLEs included 21st century skills among their
777 learning objectives and all types involved data analysis and interpretation skills;
778 Learner-experience oriented SLEs presented the most extensive list of additional
779 skills targeted (e.g., digital, computational thinking, experimentation skills), while
780 End-user oriented SLEs specialized in entrepreneurial skills and Citizen-science
781 oriented SLEs in modelling skills. Across SLE types, female participation was
782 promoted by means of female role models as stakeholder spokespersons. Career
783 opportunities were mostly facilitated through stakeholder spokespersons, as well. In
784 End-user oriented SLEs, career opportunities were particularly pronounced through
785 the iterative co-creation process followed by learners in collaboration with industry
786 partners who acted as end-users of key LPs. Challenges in Learner-experience
787 oriented SLEs and Master-product oriented SLEs pertained to formal education-
788 related constraints, while sustainability in these two types was supply-driven.
789 Challenges in End-user oriented SLEs and Citizen-science oriented SLEs converged
790 on sustaining their stakeholder networks, while they displayed demand-driven
791 sustainability. This was related to the additional demand for end-user LPs by industry
792 partners for End-user oriented SLEs or to peer networks wishing to extend data
793 collection and analysis in Citizen-science oriented SLEs.

794 Overall, the different types of SLEs we were able to identify largely
795 correspond to different strategies employed to address real-world problems in open

796 schooling projects (see Tables 3 and 4, in this regard). Learner-experience oriented
797 SLEs offered opportunities to study different dimension of a problem, which was
798 reflected in their diversity of learning objectives. An increased number of formal
799 education providers in this SLE type was obviously related to the formal education
800 constraints confronted. Master-product oriented SLEs may have been more suited for
801 developing and presenting a solution to a problem to raise awareness. This is because
802 in this SLE type a final product was singled out (master-product), which was
803 delivered at the end of the learning path, and which constructively “consumed” all
804 other prior LPs. This master-product can serve to highlight the unique selling point of
805 the solution that learners would propose. End-user oriented SLEs followed a product
806 development lifecycle to address specific needs and desires of end-users. This SLE
807 type revealed the maximum number of stakeholders, especially, industry partners.
808 Therefore, it seems quite appropriate to promote career opportunities, which can be
809 particularly pronounced through the iterative co-creation process enacted by learners
810 in close collaboration with end-users. Citizen-science oriented SLEs involved a first
811 round of learning activities, where a pre-specified methodology was employed to
812 collect and analyze data, and a second round, where new stakeholders were invited for
813 formulating policy recommendations based on the data analyzed and pursuing such
814 initiatives. Indeed, this SLE type presented the maximum number of stakeholder
815 types, which reflected a quite inclusionary approach for co-designing policy
816 recommendations with stakeholders and launching participatory initiatives.

817 Participatory scenario development exemplified the transformative potential of
818 SLEs (STE(A)M Learning Ecologies, 2024). This was most evident in the transition
819 from business-as-usual to small-effort scenarios. Indeed, the addition of just one
820 stakeholder in the SLE network could have initiated positive domino effects in the

821 form of a positive feedback loop, such that increased stakeholder synthesis and
822 interaction could lead to increased availability of learning resources and learner
823 support. Such a development would address potential bottleneck effects described in
824 business-as-usual scenarios, where teachers alone could not have effectively provided
825 all of the quality support and feedback needed by learners. A small-wins approach
826 based on such small-effort scenarios may prove decisive for scaling up open
827 schooling in the form of STE(A)M Learning Ecologies, because it exemplifies how
828 change can be possible with a relatively confined investment of time and workload.
829 Attracting even one new stakeholder can be pivotal for the dynamics in Learner-
830 experience oriented SLEs, which had the minimum number of stakeholder types as
831 well as for Master-product oriented SLEs, which had the minimum number of
832 stakeholders across SLE types. As implied by quantitative change in scenario
833 transitions in these two types of SLEs (business-as-usual to small-effort; small-effort
834 to best-case), the entry of new stakeholders should be also critical for their supply-
835 driven sustainability, which is dependent upon the provision of learning resources and
836 learner support. In End-user oriented SLEs and Citizen-science oriented SLEs,
837 however, best-case scenarios described ongoing qualitative change, related to
838 consolidated interaction between learners and end-users in the first case, and peer
839 interaction of learners and/or educators in the second. This latter change signified
840 another instance of a positive feedback loop, where peer interaction facilitated the
841 availability of learning resources and learner or peer support.

842 Building on our findings, we would like to highlight two main dimensions for
843 future research. What was observed in Citizen-science oriented SLEs may refer to
844 distributed leadership, where leadership tasks involving responsibility and decision-
845 making are no longer the privilege of school principals but are decentralized to

846 engage as many teachers as possible (see Daniëls et al., 2019). As we already
847 mentioned, citizen-science oriented SLEs favored stakeholder diversity and teacher
848 collaboration, which may reinforce their sustainability (see in this regard Wu, 2022).
849 In the same vein, distributed leadership presupposes shared ownership of initiatives to
850 promote innovation and can be fostered by both stakeholder diversity and teacher
851 collaboration. Given that peer interaction in teacher networks operating as
852 communities of practice may empower participants (Author, 2016b), it would be
853 insightful if future research examines how SLEs, Citizen-science oriented SLEs in
854 particular, can foster distributed leadership and empower teachers in planning and
855 implementing open schooling projects. This empowerment dimension is linked with
856 the second suggestion we would like to propose for future research. Stakeholders in
857 SLEs can plan their next iterations by following the same format or opting to “evolve”
858 by integrating distinguishing features of other types of SLEs. For instance, if a master
859 product is added to a Learner-experience oriented SLE, and if the participatory
860 pedagogical design is adapted accordingly (e.g., the master product is designed to
861 constructively “consume” prior LPs), then such an SLE may evolve into a Master-
862 product oriented SLE. Another example would be the evolution of a Citizen-science
863 oriented SLE into an End-user oriented SLE. In that case, the policy implications of
864 citizen science could initiate a solution-driven iteration with a co-creation process
865 between learners and stakeholders acting as end-users.

866 The pool of SLEs in the pilot phase of our project was quite confined
867 (12SLEs) and pertained to the European context, which we need to acknowledge as a
868 limitation of our study. In addition, a richer collection of metadata of learning
869 products may add insights in terms of learner creativity as well as offer the
870 opportunity to explore learner trajectories in more detail (e.g., through lag sequential

871 analysis), which would add a longitudinal perspective. The mature phase of the SLEs
872 project will offer much more data to validate and optimize the typology of SLEs.
873 However, learner and stakeholder engagement have illustrated, already in the pilot
874 phase, how SLEs can promote the creativity of all actors. They have showcased,
875 moreover, that creativity is not just leisure (see here Henriksen et al., 2017) but can be
876 materialized in pedagogical designs and LPs, which can bridge formal and non-formal
877 learning settings. SLEs can provide a delicate balance between structure and
878 guidance, on the one hand, which are the norm in formal education, and agency and
879 freedom, on the other, allowing students, their teachers, and multiple stakeholders to
880 benefit from heterogeneous resources and co-create novel and useful solutions to
881 address real-world problems (see Author et al., 2017). Teachers can employ the
882 concept of SLEs as a robust instructional strategy to support students in developing
883 21st century skills (see in this regard Varas et al., 2023). Artefacts constructed by
884 learners when using learning resources provided by stakeholders can be exploited as
885 organizing principles of coherent pedagogical designs and learner experiences in
886 SLEs. There were several implementations of design thinking models in STEM
887 education and open schooling, which all aimed to engage learners in designing,
888 producing, and testing artefacts to address real-world problems (e.g. Authors et al.,
889 2023a; Liu et al., 2023; Wingard et al., 2022). Solutions to these problems were often
890 user-tailored, for which stakeholder input and feedback was sought and elaborated
891 upon. Indeed, outdoor activities and stakeholder engagement were found to enhance
892 student creativity through manufacturing artefacts (Lage-Gómez & Ros, 2024). We
893 believe that there is much potential for delving deeper in the overlap between design
894 thinking and creativity (Gabriel et al., 2016; He et al., 2023). Future research should

895 exploit SLEs with their creative pedagogical design and artefacts to weigh optimal
896 mixes of guidance and freedom across different types of open schooling projects.

897

898 **Endnotes**

899 ¹ Details of the stakeholder synthesis for each SLE can be found in the SLEs portfolio

900 at this link: <https://www.steamecologies.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/SLEs->

901 [PORTFOLIO-TEMPLATE_v1.2.pdf](https://www.steamecologies.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/SLEs-PORTFOLIO-TEMPLATE_v1.2.pdf)

902

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1034 **Figure legends**

1035

1036 Figure 1

1037 Bird feeders in the Learner-experience oriented STE(A)M Learning Ecology titled
1038 “Steaming up with nature’s wonders” (Romania, Ramnicu Valcea).

1039

1040 Figure 2

1041 Pollination robotics in the Learner-experience oriented STE(A)M Learning Ecology
1042 titled “Steaming up with nature’s wonders” (Romania, Ramnicu Valcea).

1043

1044 Figure 3

1045 Drawings of plant species used for learners’ botanical e-book in the Master-product
1046 oriented STE(A)M Learning Ecology titled “AI in ecology – ecology in AI”
1047 (Slovakia, Poprad).

1048

1049 Figure 4

1050 Demo of a solution for digitalizing port management (map client for displaying port
1051 data) in the End-user oriented STE(A)M Learning Ecology titled “Student software
1052 solutions for real clients” (Norway, Trondheim).

1053

1054 Figure 5

1055 Testing a seismograph in the Citizen-science oriented STE(A)M Learning Ecology
1056 titled “Studying earthquakes” (Greece, Athens).

1057

1058

1059 Figure 6

1060

1061 Figure 6. Types of STE(A)M Learning Ecologies (open schooling projects). Dark
1062 rhombuses represent learning products delivered by learners (i.e. artefacts constructed
1063 by learners themselves, anytime they used learning resources to enact learning
1064 activities); the dark line running through learning products represents the learning
1065 path and activity sequence. In Learner-experience oriented SLEs (1), learning
1066 activities and the delivery of learning products do not follow any strict serial sequence
1067 but can be switched in order, without that having any impact on the learning path.
1068 This is depicted visually by the cyclical arrangement of learning products. In Master-
1069 product oriented SLEs (2), one final learning product is singled out (master-product),
1070 which is delivered at the end of the learning activity sequence, and which integrates
1071 all prior learning products or needs them to be created. This configuration is portrayed
1072 by arrows starting from all learning products and heading towards the master-product.
1073 In End-user oriented SLEs (3), the learning path evolves along an iterative process,
1074 where learners co-create and optimize in close collaboration with end-users 0a key
1075 learning product, which addresses concrete end-user needs and desires. This is
1076 represented by the helix-shaped learning activity sequence. In Citizen-science
1077 oriented SLEs (4), the learning activity sequence involves two phases: First, learners
1078 follow a pre-specified methodology to collect and analyze data (continuous cycle on
1079 the top); second, they formulate policy recommendations based on their data, and
1080 invite new stakeholders in the SLE to pursue these initiatives (dashed cycle at the
1081 bottom).

1082 **Appendix A. Template for participatory pedagogical design***

Main themes for participatory pedagogical design	Tasks	Examples
(1) Learning products to be created by students themselves along learning paths	Please describe artefacts that are expected by learners in the above learning sequence; can you please give texts, graphs, drawings, sketches, demos, mockups, etc., for these learning products?	Any artefact that will be created by learners during enacting learning activities, e.g., texts, graphs, models, digital artefacts, and any other product manufactured by learners using learning resources.
(2) Potential learning paths; how learning resources can be arranged to form learning paths	Please describe the sequence of learning activities in the SLE pilot. Which learning resources are necessary for these learning activities? Is there one path to take only or can learners have alternative learning paths? Please explain.	Which learning products are expected first and which next? Is any learning product necessary for creating another learning product in the learning activity sequence?
(3) Curriculum mapping of knowledge and skills as	Which targeted knowledge and skills are	Correspondence of knowledge and skills

reflected by learning products	reflected in these learning products? Please match knowledge and skills	reflected by learning products to curriculum standards for corresponding subjects
(4) Support and guidance to be provided by stakeholders to students along learning paths	Please describe how stakeholders can guide and support students while using learning resources to enact learning activities	E.g., Elaborate on the usability of certain apps; scaffold data collection and analysis
(5) Opportunities for female engagement	Please describe how the learning path may attract both males and females	E.g., Selection of topics; female representatives or spokespersons acting as role models
(6) Career opportunities	Please describe how stakeholders involved in the SLE pilot can inspire learners' career paths	E.g., Career opportunities promoted through stakeholder representatives in key positions (public, private, and civil society organizations)

1083 *Note: A completed participatory pedagogical design template from the STE(A)M

1084 Learning Ecology in Cyprus is provided as Supplemental Online Material.

1085 **Appendix B. Participatory scenario development for the Butterfly project (CY)**

	Business-as-usual scenario (Baseline conditions, crucial gaps and inconsistencies to address when implementing SLEs)	Small-effort scenario (Small-scale inputs potentially decisive for achieving considerable progress in the short-term)	Best-case scenario (Ideal conditions for SLEs to flourish and secure long-term sustainability)
Stakeholder synthesis	The Butterfly project is part of a European initiative which employs the same methodology to gather and analyze butterfly data from multiple European locations. In Cyprus, the project was initiated by the Ministry of Education, Sport and Youth (Unit for Education for the Environment and Sustainable Development) under the support of the Open University of Cyprus. A secondary	The University of Cyprus (Research in Science and Technology Education Group) joined the project as National Coordinator in the SLEs project and the Butterfly project was the pilot SLE selected in Cyprus. Additional stakeholders, which joined the stakeholder coalition, are the Local Municipality of Pera Chorio and the Museum of Natural History in Dali,	Other stakeholders sought to join the network and foster its strengths and sustainability were: (1) The Department of Forests in Cyprus, which may adopt student recommendations to enhance flora and butterfly diversity and support butterfly pollination; (2) firms offering gardener services in the wider area of Nicosia may provide additional learning resources and integrate student

	school teacher in a school near Nicosia adopted it from a colleague of hers.	which hosts an exhibition of the butterfly project.	recommendations in their business model.
Stakeholder interaction	The teacher tries to bring additional stakeholders in the project through personal initiatives and interpersonal relationships, which is restricted by time constraints, lack of resources, and total workload. A main barrier for scaling up the project is that it is perceived as an extracurricular initiative.	Stakeholder collaboration is currently concentrating on the local scale, around the neighborhood. Stakeholders start integrating parts of the butterfly project in their planning. The Local Municipality has offered considerable funding for the construction of a park, which will be supported by the SLE.	Provided that quality control is maintained in data collection and processing, the project may mature into a fully-fledged citizen science initiative with considerable implications for spatial planning and the overall aim to increase flora and butterfly diversity for butterfly pollination.
Learning resources available	Resources available mainly stem from the Open University of Cyprus and include: (1) A guide with the methodology for butterfly data	Stakeholders “inherit” the learning products of student projects and make them available to other students, who can use them as learning resources; this	Provided that more stakeholders join, especially the Department of Forests in Cyprus and firms offering gardener services, these are expected to offer

collection; (2) a digital tool for identifying butterfly species; (3) a database for storing butterfly data.

is currently facilitated through the contribution of the Natural Museum of Dali, which hosts learning products of the butterfly project

additional learning resources and increase the variety of learning products, which can be expected from the butterfly project.

Support provided to learners

The teacher works mostly on her own to support students in data collection and processing. Support by the Open University of Cyprus is crucial but not enough to account for all learner needs and desires.

Learners are supported by two higher education institutes, the Local Municipality and the Museum of Natural History in data collection and processing and in formulating policy implications based on their data analysis.

Learners connect with other SLEs in the wider European “Butterfly” initiative; they exchange knowledge, experiences, and learning products; peer and teacher support from other SLEs is available and a community of practice is formed.

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1088 Table 1. Descriptive characteristics of STE(A)M Learning Ecologies

STE(A)M Learning Ecology	Challenge	Initiator; National Coordinator (when different from Initiator)	Country, city	Learners' age
Intertwined – Mosaic of the community brain	Teenagers' lack of engagement with the local library and its maker space	Ballybane Community Library; National University of Ireland Galway	Ireland (IE), Galway	15
Student software solutions for real clients	Support university students transition from academic settings to the professional world	Norwegian University of Science and Technology	Norway (NO), Trondheim	21-24
Imagining the world in 2030	Raising awareness on the ethical and environmental opportunities and threats of AI	Domus - Museos Científicos Coruñeses	Spain (ES), A Coruña	15-16
The butterfly project	Contribute to data collection and analysis of butterfly species in local ecosystems	Cyprus Ministry of Education, Sport and Youth; University of Cyprus	Cyprus (CY), Nicosia	16
Green citizenship in action	Need for new practical models for more sustainable schools and communities	Agency for the Promotion of European Research	Italy (IT), Rome	11

Ecosystem services from land to sea	Need to increase students' awareness on UN Sustainable Development Goals	Centro Ciência Viva do Algarve	Portugal (PT), Faro	9-10
Steaming up with nature's wonders	Need for students to reconnect with nature, especially local nature	Mircea ceL Batran National College; European Schoolnet	Romania (RO), Ramnicu Valcea	6-7
AI in ecology – ecology in AI	Lack of students' engagement in the conservation of the local ecosystem	Poprad Primary School; European Schoolnet	Slovakia (SK), Poprad	13
Energies for the future	Need for younger generations to be aware about climate change and renewable energy	WISTA Management GmbH and Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin	Germany (DE), Berlin	12-16
Psychological health and wellbeing	Create a gym for physical education in the Patrijarh Pavle Gymnasium	Center for the Promotion of Science	Serbia (RS), Belgrade	5-19
Studying earthquakes	Understand earthquakes and increase awareness of civic protection	Ellinogermaniki Agogi	Greece (GR), Pallini-Athens	13-16
GIRLS4STEM	Counteract gender stereotypes with female STEM professionals acting as role models	Directorate for STEM & VET Programmes	Malta (MT), Pembroke	12-13

1090 Table 2. Stakeholders and learners in STE(A0M Learning Ecologies

STE(A)M Learning Ecology	Formal education providers	Non-formal education providers	Governmental organizations	Civil society organizations	Industry partners	Total number of stakeholders	No of stakeholder types	No of learners
Intertwined – Mosaic of the community brain (IE)	2	3	0	0	1	6	3	37
Student software solutions for real clients (NO)	1	0	1	0	11	13	3	65
Imagining the world in 2030 (ES)	1	1	1	1	1	5	5	11
The butterfly project (CY)	3	1	3	0	2	9	4	23
Green citizenship in action (IT)	2	0	3	1	0	6	3	11

Ecosystem services from land to sea (PT)	4	4	1	1	1	11	5	188
Steaming up with nature's wonders (RO)	3	3	1	0	0	7	3	21
AI in ecology – ecology in AI (SK)	2	1	0	1	0	4	3	20
Energies for the future (DE)	3	3	3	0	3	12	4	15
Psychological health and wellbeing (RS)	2	1	1	1	3	8	5	450
Studying earthquakes (GR)	2	1	1	1	1	6	5	175
GIRLS4STEM (MT)	3	2	3	1	0	9	4	60

1092 Table 3. Typology of STE(A)M Learning Ecologies.

	Learner-experience oriented SLEs	Master-product oriented SLEs	End-user oriented SLEs	Citizen-science oriented SLEs
Learning path including learning resources and learning products	Learners deliver a rich portfolio of diverse learning products making use of dedicated learning resources offered by stakeholders in the SLE	Learner work is converging on a master learning product delivered at the end of the learning path, which integrates all prior learning products	Learners follow a number of iterations to deliver a key learning product, which addresses concrete end-user (stakeholder) needs and desires	Learners follow a pre-specified methodology to contribute to data collection and analysis supported by multiple social actors in multiple locations
Sequencing of learning activities	SLEs in this category are quite modular, in the sense that learning activities do not follow any strict serial sequence but can be switched in order	Learner engagement serves the creation of the master product, which can be presented to external audiences and utilized for launching policy initiatives	Product development lifecycle; marked resemblance with iterative engineering design process and analogous approaches (e.g. model-based inquiry)	Learners get familiarized with the methodology, collect data, insert them into a broader database, analyse data, and conclude with policy implications

Flexibility in pedagogical design	Learning activities and learning products can be either skipped or added without any major impact on the learning path and overall learner experience	Overall structure dictated by the features of the master product; prior learning products may be adapted to suit different learning settings	Unique designs focused on end-user needs and desires; learners and end-users maintain contact throughout the duration of the SLE to adapt designs	Further opportunities for stakeholder engagement and extension of the SLE in terms of policy recommendations and initiatives
Trade-offs	More learning activities and products may enhance learner experience in the short term at the expense of coherence and long-term learning outcomes	Time and workload for learners and stakeholders needs to be effectively allocated to all necessary prior learning products as well as the master product	Learners and end-users need to be creative and, at the same time, be able to narrow down options to maintain realism and cost-effectiveness	Stakeholders and learners need to strike an optimal balance between the rigidity of the methodology and innovation in terms of policy initiatives
Examples	IE; IT; PT; RO; DE; MT	ES; SK	NO; RS	CY; GR

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1095 Table 4. Similarities and differences between types of STE(A)M Learning Ecologies.

	Learner-experience oriented SLEs	Master-product oriented SLEs	End-user oriented SLEs	Citizen-science oriented SLEs
Stakeholder synthesis	Minimum number of stakeholder types; maximum number of formal and non- formal education providers	Minimum number of stakeholders	Maximum number of stakeholders; maximum number of industry partners	Maximum number of stakeholder types
Learning objectives	21 st century skills; data analysis and interpretation skills; digital and/or computational thinking skills and/or experimentation skills	21 st century skills; data analysis and interpretation skills	21 st century skills; data analysis and interpretation skills; entrepreneurial skills	21 st century skills; data analysis and interpretation skills; modelling skills
Female participation	Female role models	Female role models	Female role models	Female role models

Career opportunities	Stakeholder spokespersons	Stakeholder spokespersons	Particularly pronounced through the iterative co-creation process	Stakeholder spokespersons
Change	Transformative change in small-effort scenarios; increasing number of stakeholders increases availability of learning resources and learner support; quantitative change in best-case scenarios	Transformative change in small-effort scenarios; increasing number of stakeholders increases availability of learner support; quantitative change in best-case scenarios	Transformative change in small-effort scenarios; increasing number of stakeholders increases availability of learner support; qualitative change in best-case scenarios	Transformative change in small-effort scenarios; peer interaction increases availability of learning resources and learner support; qualitative change in best-case scenarios
Challenges	Formal education constraints	Formal education constraints	Sustain stakeholder network	Sustain stakeholder network
Sustainability	Supply-driven	Supply-driven	Demand-driven	Demand-driven
Examples	IE; IT; PT; RO; DE; MT	ES; SK	NO; RS	CY; GR

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The screenshot shows a web application interface for creating and managing objects on a map. The map displays a coastal area with buildings and water. A data entry form is visible on the right side of the screen. The form includes the following fields:

- NAME
- UNICODE
- Aufahrtstyp (dropdown menu)
- Berichtsart (dropdown menu)
- Weg herleitet (checkbox)
- Dato Tølgangstid (text input)
- HavnNavn (text input)
- Havnstøtthavn (text input)
- Informasjon (text input)
- Kalibrer (text input)
- Datofangstid (dropdown menu)
- Dato Tølgangstid (text input)
- Havnstøtthavn (text input)
- Havnstøtthavn (text input)
- Weg herleitet (checkbox)
- Kalibrer (text input)
- Kalibrer (text input)

A tooltip is visible over the 'Dato Tølgangstid' field, displaying the text: 'Dato for opstarten af den første tølgangstid (førstegangstid) i havnen.'

- Can create new objects, place them on the map and save
- Each field has a description
- Mandatory fields are shown with a red *
- There is user feedback if a field is missing a value

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(1) Learner-experience oriented SLEs

(2) Master-product oriented SLEs

(3) End-user oriented SLEs

(4) Citizen-science oriented SLEs

1107